

THERMO-OPTIC DESIGNS FOR MICROWAVE AND MILLIMETER-WAVE ELECTRIC-FIELD PROBES

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Abstract

We have considered various thermo-optic designs for electric-field probes for the approximate frequency range of 1-110 GHz. The designs are all based on using an optically sensed thermometer to measure the temperature rise of a resistive material in an electric field. This paper presents calculations of the sensitivities of the different designs, measurement results for the most easily fabricated design, and a discussion of possible improvements. Our results indicate that a probe based on this design could detect a minimum electric field of about 30-50 V/m.

I. Introduction

Increasing activity at frequencies in the millimeter-wave and upper microwave range brings with it a need for electric-field (E-field) probes for these very high frequencies. The use which occasioned the present work is as a transfer-standard probe, but other applications (e.g., as a hazard meter) are also possible. The frequency range of interest is approximately 1-110 GHz, with the 26-110 GHz range of particular interest for this project. E-field probes developed at the National Institute of Standards and Technology in the past have primarily been of the dipole-diode design [1,2], and we are continuing to pursue this option for frequencies higher than the present maximum of 18 GHz. It does not appear likely that the dipole-diode design can be extended beyond about 40 GHz, however, and therefore we are also investigating other probe designs. In this paper we present designs which use an optically sensed thermometer to measure the temperature rise of a resistive structure in an electric field [3]. Such thermo-optic (TO) probe designs appear to hold more promise for frequencies above 40 GHz than does the dipole-diode design, and they have other desirable traits besides their frequency response. Like the resistive leads of the dipole-diode probes, the optical fiber linking the resistive sensor and the metering unit does not itself pick up stray signals, nor does it perturb the field to be measured. In addition, unlike the diode detector [4], thermally sensed probes respond to the total $|E|^2$, even in the presence of multiple frequencies. The poor sensitivity characteristic of thermal probes is a problem, but very broadband frequency response can be achieved.

In the sections below, we first present theoretical background for the TO design and several specific configurations of it. This is followed by a discussion of the experimental setup and results of measurements made on TO probe tips. The measurement results are then compared to theoretical expectations, and we conclude with a summary and suggestions for possible improvements.

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II. Theoretical Background

The TO designs we consider are based on a commercially produced optically sensed thermometer [5]. The sensing element of the thermometer consists of a very small amount (about 40 μg) of a phosphorescent material affixed to the end of an optical fiber. When the phosphor is excited by a pulse of light sent up the fiber, the lifetime of the excited state depends on the temperature of the phosphor. By measuring the light emitted back down the fiber by the phosphor, one can therefore measure the temperature of the phosphor and anything with which it is in thermal equilibrium. We consider several different configurations of TO probes, calculating a predicted response (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for a fixed field level) for each as a function of frequency. In each calculation, we first obtained the power absorbed in a given electric field and then calculated the rise in the temperature of the phosphor with that particular design. The various geometrical and electrical parameters (length, conductivity, etc.) were then varied in order to maximize the temperature rise for a given field strength. Three basic configurations were investigated, and we present the results for each.

Thin Strip

The first configuration, which we call the thin-strip design, consists of a thin film of resistive material deposited on the phosphor and the fiber. Initial calculations led us to choose a thin rectangular strip deposited on a wedge-shaped phosphor tip, as shown in fig. 1 (a). The power absorbed by the strip was calculated earlier [6]. For a strip with dimensions $2\ell \times w \times t$ and conductivity σ , the absorbed power is

$$P_{abs} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{E_r^2 \ell_{eff}^2}{|Z_{in}|^2} R_{abs}, \quad (1a)$$

where

$$Z_{in} = R_{abs} + Z_r,$$

$$R_{abs} = \frac{\ell}{\sigma w t} \frac{1}{\sin^2 k\ell} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2k\ell} \sin 2k\ell\right), \quad (1b)$$

$$\ell_{eff} = \frac{2(1 - \cos k\ell)}{k \sin k\ell}, \quad k = 2\pi/\lambda.$$

Fig. 1. TO design configurations.

E_z is the component of the electric field along the length of the strip, and $Z_r = R_r + jX_r$ is the radiation impedance of a center-fed, rectangular-strip dipole. Expressions for R_r and X_r can be found in [6]. In order to relate the temperature rise of the phosphor to the power absorbed by the strip, the following approximations were made: the phosphor was taken to be a circular cylinder of radius r and length c ; the strip was assumed to cover the top surface of the phosphor; the bottom surface of the phosphor was held at the ambient temperature; and all the heat absorbed by the strip was assumed transferred to the phosphor. The following form can then be obtained for the rise in temperature, averaged over the volume of the phosphor,

$$\langle \Delta T_{ph} \rangle = \frac{4r}{A_s k_{ph}} P_{abs} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\beta_n^3} \frac{\cosh(\beta_n c/r) - 1}{\sinh(\beta_n c/r)}, \quad (2)$$

where A_s is the area covered by the strip, k_{ph} is the thermal conductivity of the phosphor, β_n is the n th zero of the zero-order Bessel function, and P_{abs} is given by eq. (1). If we maximize $\langle \Delta T_{ph} \rangle$ to determine the optimal values of σ and t , we find that they occur for

$$\sigma t = \frac{\ell}{w |Z_r|} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2k\ell} \sin 2k\ell \right) \frac{1}{\sin^2 k\ell}. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) gives the value of surface resistivity (σt) which will yield the maximum sensitivity, but that optimal value is frequency dependent. The choice of the frequency at which σt is optimized (f_{opt}) affects not only the sensitivity, but also the frequency response of the probe. The same is true of the length of strip (2ℓ). To investigate the trade-offs involved we computed and plotted $\langle \Delta T_{ph} \rangle$ as a function of frequency for various choices of ℓ and f_{opt} . The values which gave the greatest sensitivity, while still maintaining an acceptable frequency response, were $2\ell = 2$ mm and $f_{opt} = 10$ GHz which result in $1/(\sigma t) = 321 \Omega$ for a square sample. These are the values that were used to obtain the "thin strip" results, which are used in the comparison of the different designs shown in fig. 2. The figure plots the temperature rise versus frequency for each design in an applied field of 100 V/m. With the fluoroptic thermometer we can now detect temperature rises of about 0.04 °C. As can be seen from the figure, even with all parameters optimized the thin-strip design is too insensitive to be of use. We estimate that the minimum detectable field with this design would be about 365 V/m.

Thin Phosphor Substrate

The second TO design consists of a thin resistive strip deposited on a thin ($\leq 50 \mu\text{m}$) substrate of phosphorescent material. This phosphor substrate is then viewed remotely (about $25 \mu\text{m}$) by the fiber, as depicted in fig. 1 (b). This design will be referred to as the thin-phosphor design. The electromagnetic aspects of the design are the same as in the thin-strip design discussed above, and the power absorbed by the thin rectangular strip is again given by eq. (1). The heat transfer properties of this design are very different, however, because the phosphor is sur-

Fig. 2. Predicted responses of different TO designs.

rounded by air rather than attached to a heat sink (the fiber), and also because the heat from the strip is not transferred effectively to the entire mass of phosphor but only to the part below the strip. For this geometry the rise in temperature of the phosphor below the resistive strip is given by

$$\Delta T_{ph} = \frac{P_{abs}}{2\ell wh (2 + ht/k_{ph})}, \quad (4)$$

where h is the power lost to the air per unit area and temperature difference (taken to be $10 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{°C})$), and k_{ph} is again the thermal conductivity of the phosphor ($0.81 \text{ W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{°C})$).

As was done for the thin-strip design, the optimal value of σt was calculated and again was found to depend on frequency. After comparing the sensitivities and frequency responses for various values of ℓ and f_{opt} , we chose $2\ell = 2$ mm and $f_{opt} = 10$ GHz as the best values. We also checked the response to fields parallel to the width of the strip, and these considerations led us to choose a width of 0.5 mm. Using these optimal values of the parameters, the "thin-phosphor" results of fig. 2 follow. This design is clearly far superior to the thin-strip design, and these calculations indicate it could detect fields as small as 34 V/m. The frequency response is excellent, within a factor of 2 of the maximum from 10 GHz to 110 GHz. If this design is to be pursued, however, the practical problems of fabricating a thin phosphor slab and supporting it without a heat sink would have to be solved.

Resistive Sphere

The third geometry we consider is a resistive sphere surrounding the phosphor and end of the fiber, with the phosphor situated at the center of the

sphere, as shown in fig. 1 (c). For calculational ease we neglect the electromagnetic effect of the fiber and phosphor and approximate the probe tip as a resistive sphere. The power it absorbs in an electric field is then given by the classic result of Mie [7]. Since this result is rather long, unenlightening, and available in many texts [8,9], we shall not reproduce it here. There are two heat-loss mechanisms for this geometry, conduction by the fiber and by the air. The temperature rise of the phosphor is given approximately by

$$\Delta T_{ph} = P_{abs} / (\pi R k_f + 4\pi r^2 h), \quad (5)$$

where R is the fiber radius, k_f is its thermal conductivity (taken to be $0.76 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$), r is the sphere radius, h is as in eq. (4), and P_{abs} is obtained from the Mie results. Optimum values of the phosphor radius, conductivity, and dielectric constant were found by plotting the results for various values of the parameters. The results are not very sensitive to the value of the dielectric constant. The optimal values of r and σ were found to be about 1 mm and 10 S/m respectively. The "volume-heating" curve of fig. 2 then results. Although it does not go to as low a frequency as the thin-phosphor result, the frequency response is still good. The sensitivity is adequate, with fields as small as 45 V/m detectable.

If the conductivity is too much larger than 10 S/m , the field will not penetrate into the volume of the material, and only the outer shell will be heated directly by the induced current. As an example we consider a sphere of solid carbon surrounding the phosphor. Although carbon is not a particularly good conductor, its conductivity ($7.3 \times 10^4 \text{ S/m}$ for graphite) far exceeds 10 S/m , and therefore the induced current will be limited to an outer shell with thickness equal to the skin depth (about $20 \mu\text{m}$). This design shares several qualitative features with the thin strip design, and consequently we do not expect it to be very sensitive. This expectation is confirmed by the "spherical-shell" results of fig. 2, obtained with a radius of 1 mm and $\sigma = 7.3 \times 10^4 \text{ S/m}$. Based on these results the minimum detectable electric field for this design is about 260 V/m .

III. Measurements

Description

Several probe tips of the resistive-sphere design were obtained. The tips varied in the size and in the composition of the resistive sphere. All the tips were tested, but we will present only one full set of results. These are for the most sensitive of the tips, a sphere of radius 0.91 mm , made of carbon mixed in a resin binder. Some results will also be presented for a tip of the same composition, with radius 0.625 mm . A potential difficulty which should be noted is that the calculations assume a constant conductivity, and this is required for the flat frequency response at high frequencies. (We are including all loss effects, including $\text{Im } \epsilon$, in an effective σ .) It is not certain that the particular carbon-resin mixture that is used has a constant conductivity over the $20\text{-}110 \text{ GHz}$ range.

Tests were performed in the anechoic chamber to measure the heating of the tips when exposed to a

known electric field. On the basis of past experience and preliminary tests it was deemed desirable to enclose the tips in some electromagnetically transparent material such as foam in order to shield them from drafts in the anechoic chamber. A block of closed-cell foam containing a cavity was constructed for this purpose, but comparison of measurements on coated and uncoated tips, inside and outside the block, indicated that the block itself was being heated and was in turn heating the probes. Therefore a thin-walled box was built of the same foam, and this configuration provided shielding without extraneous heating.

Two probes were used in all the measurements, one with the carbon-coated tip which was supposed to register a temperature rise in response to an applied electromagnetic field, and one ordinary uncoated probe to monitor the ambient temperature within the box. Both probes were oriented with their fibers perpendicular to the electric field. The magnitude of the change in the difference between the readings of the two probes should indicate the strength of the applied field. Data acquisition software was written to read the output of the two probes, averaging over a preset number of samples and computing the statistical uncertainty of the average (s/\sqrt{N}) in the set of samples for each probe. It also computes the difference in the readings of the two probes, again obtaining the average and uncertainty for the given number of measurements. In this manner we can monitor the response of each probe individually, as well as their difference. By averaging over sets of 150 samples in all the measurements, we were able to achieve statistical uncertainties of about 0.02°C in the difference between the readings of the two probes. (The time required for a set of 150 measurements was about 20 s .) In all the measurements the readings were allowed to stabilize within about 0.02°C before the field was turned on, while it was on, and after it was turned off.

Results

Measurements were made between 12.5 and 18 GHz , at 26.5 GHz , and at 36 GHz . The maximum field levels we could obtain at 26.5 and 36 GHz were 40.9 V/m and 20.1 V/m respectively, which were insufficient to produce a measurable response in any of the probes. At the lower frequencies, much more power was available, and we measured temperature rise as a function of field strength at 16 GHz , and as a function of frequency ($12.5\text{-}18 \text{ GHz}$) for a 539 V/m field. Plots of the results are presented in fig. 3-5. Figure 3 shows the time dependence of the response to an applied field of 815 V/m at 16 GHz . The times at which the field was turned on and off are indicated by arrows. The initial response occurs within about 2 min. , but there may be an additional small rise in ΔT for about 7 min. Figure 4 plots the probe response as a function of the plane-wave power density incident on the probe at a frequency of 16 GHz . The temperature rise is linear in power density, as it should be. Furthermore, the line extrapolates back very close to $\Delta T = 0$ at zero power density. In fig. 5 we have plotted the response as a function of frequency for an electric field strength of 539 V/m . The absence of an effect at 26.5 GHz for a 40.3 V/m field would translate into an upper bound of $\Delta T < 7.2^\circ\text{C}$ at 26.5 GHz . We have also included in fig. 5 the results of measurements on a smaller carbon-coated probe ($r = 0.625 \text{ mm}$) of similar composition.

Figure 3. Difference in temperature between coated and uncoated probe tips, as a function of time, at 16 GHz and $E = 815.2$ V/m.

Figure 5. Change in difference in temperature between coated and uncoated probes, as a function of frequency, at $E = 539$ V/m.

Figure 4. Change in difference in temperature between coated and uncoated probes, as a function of incident power density, at 16 GHz.

Discussion

There are three features of interest in comparing the experimental results to theoretical expectations — the dependence of the response on the sphere radius, the overall size of the response, and its frequency dependence. The predicted dependence on the sphere radius is given by eq. (5). For the frequencies and dimensions of these measurements the absorbed power is approximately proportional to r^3 . Therefore ΔT should be proportional to r^3 if conduction by the fiber is the dominant heat-loss mechanism for the carbon sphere, whereas if most of the heat is lost to the surrounding air ΔT should vary as r^1 . Using our approximate values for h and k_f ,

we expect that about five times as much heat should be lost to the fiber as is lost to the air (for the larger sphere). If we assume that ΔT is proportional to a power of r , $\Delta T \propto r^\alpha$, and combine the values and uncertainties of α for the four different frequencies measured, then our best value for α is 2.84 ± 0.28 . This is consistent with all the heat being lost to the fiber, but does not preclude some heat loss to the air. To estimate the relative amounts of each we write ΔT as

$$\Delta T = r^3 a(f)/(1 + br^2), \quad (6)$$

where br^2 is the amount of heat lost to the air relative to that lost to the fiber for a sphere of radius r . For the larger carbon tip ($r = 0.91$ mm) we obtain $br^2 = -0.12 \pm 0.21$, indicating that while most of the heat is lost to the fiber, as much as 10-20% could be lost to the air. This is in approximate agreement with our expectations. The practical importance is that it indicates that the sensitivity of this design can be increased significantly by reducing the thermal contact between sphere and fiber.

A direct comparison of theory and experiment for the magnitude and frequency dependence of the response is not possible because we do not know the conductivity of the carbon-composite sphere. We therefore computed the response $\Delta T(f)$ for values of σ ranging from 1 S/m to 10^5 S/m. The theoretical predictions are roughly the same size as the measured results for values of σ from 20 S/m to about 10^4 S/m. Because of the uncertainty in the values of various parameters, agreement within a factor of 2-5 is all one can expect. There is, however, no value of σ for which the theoretical results can match the steep slope of the data, and the slope depends only on σ and on r , which is known well. The largest predicted slope, which occurs for $\sigma \approx 20$ S/m, is a factor of almost 2 smaller than the observed slope in the 12-18 GHz range. This is illustrated in fig 6. The steep slope of the data could be due to a variation of σ across this frequency range, but it seems unlikely that σ could vary rapidly enough. A more plausible explanation might be that the fiber and phosphor in

Fig 6. Observed and predicted ($\sigma = 20$ S/m) frequency responses for $r = 0.91$ mm.

the sphere reduce its effective radius. That would shift the predicted curve to the right, resulting in a steeper predicted slope (and lower predicted response) in the 12-18 GHz range.

IV Summary

Several thermo-optic E-field probe designs were investigated, and the resistive sphere design was chosen for fabrication and testing. The probe tips tested were not very sensitive, but it may be possible to improve the sensitivity enough to make a useful probe. Although the measured frequency response was not flat, it was not expected to be flat over the frequency range of the measurements. Unfortunately, above 18 GHz insufficient power was available to determine whether the frequency response does become flat. The frequency dependence of the sensitivity in the 12-18 GHz range agrees qualitatively but not quantitatively with the theoretical predictions. The quantitative discrepancy may be due to a frequency-dependent conductivity of the carbon-resin sphere or to the effects of the phosphor and fiber in the sphere. The isotropy and stability of the resistive-sphere probe tips have not yet been tested.

There are several possible ways to improve the performance of TO E-field probes. Use of a larger resistive sphere would increase the sensitivity and would also shift the low-frequency cutoff to lower frequency. It would not avoid problems with the frequency dependence of σ , however, if such problems exist. Sensitivity would also be improved if we could reduce the heat lost to the optical fiber by the resistive sphere and the phosphor. The most promising option at this time appears to be the thin phosphor configuration. This configuration should have significantly greater sensitivity, and it should also have a constant conductivity since the resistive material is a thin metal strip. Additional increase in sensitivity could be made by using a more sensitive optically sensed thermometer. A newer model is available with a precision about five times better

than that used in our measurements. It is not clear how much of this increase could be effectively utilized, but a factor of at least 2 seems feasible.

If the sensitivity of these TO probes can indeed be increased and if the theoretical frequency dependence is achieved, this would be a very attractive technology for E-field probes. The probes would be small, nonperturbing, EMI resistant, and responsive to total $|E|^2$; would operate at very high frequencies; and would probably be isotropic.

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References

- [1] E.B. Larsen and F.X. Ries, "Design and calibration of the NBS isotropic electric-field monitor (EFM-5), 0.2 to 1000 MHz," NBS Tech. Note 1033, March 1981.
- [2] M. Kanda and L.D. Driver, "An isotropic electric-field probe with tapered resistive dipoles for broad-band use, 100 kHz to 18 GHz," *IEEE Trans. MTT-35*, no. 2, 124-130, February 1987.
- [3] V.M. Martin, R.M. Segal, and R. Durham, "Fiber optic microwave power probe," *Optical Eng.* 26, no. 2, 170-173, February 1987.
- [4] J. Randa and M. Kanda, "Multiple-source, multiple-frequency error of an electric-field meter," *IEEE Trans. AP-33*, no. 1, 2-9, January 1985.
- [5] K.A. Wickersheim and M.H. Sun, "Fluoroptic thermometry," *Measurement and Control*, p. 132, June 1987.
- [6] J. Randa, M. Kanda, and D. Melquist, "Possible designs for electric-field-strength probes for millimeter waves," NBSIR 88-3084, February 1988.
- [7] G. Mie, *Ann. Physik* 25, no. 4, 377, 1908.
- [8] J. Stratton, *Electromagnetic Theory*. New York: McGraw Hill, 1941, ch. 9.
- [9] M. Born and E. Wolf, *Principles of Optics*. New York: Pergamon Press, 1965, ch. 13.